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SoildiverAgro

Soil biodiversity enhancement in European agroecosystems to promote their stability and resilience by external inputs reduction and crop performance increase

D2.3 – OUTCOMES FROM REGIONAL WORKSHOPS ABOUT PROPOSED MANAGEMENT PRACTICES

Universidade de Vigo

D2.3. OUTCOMES FROM REGIONAL WORKSHOPS ABOUT PROPOSED MANAGEMENT PRACTICES

Summary

Six different regional workshops have been organized in the six pedoclimatic regions where SoildiverAgro is working (Mediterranean South, Lusitanian, Atlantic Central, Continental, Nemoral and Boreal), conceived as informative and discussion sessions hold by the Regional Coordinators, addressed to all stakeholders and people interested on soil biodiversity and sustainable agriculture in the region. This interaction with regional stakeholders forms part of a multi-actor approach set up from the beginning of the project, that involves and looks for the interaction of key stakeholders during all project lifetime. Hence, the main goals of the workshops were to:

- I. Show all results achieved during the first year of the project in WP2 (tasks 2.1 and 2.2), showing the outcomes of a general literature research, data-mining, meta-analysis, surveys and discussions groups. The focus was put in identifying potential cropping systems, agricultural practices and strategies to be used in synergistic combination for soil biodiversity enhancement, acknowledging the fact that the adoption of a single systems/practice/strategy would not be enough to face all the identified agronomic, socioeconomic and environmental problems while overcoming technical constraints, economic costs and social acceptance.
- II. Present the experimental design of the case studies implemented in the each region for WP5 and WP6, based on the participative process with stakeholders, so that we provide solutions to the cultivation of the selected crops by the management of soil biodiversity, in search of finding the relationship between soil biological groups and crop production and quality.

This procedure involves that only those strategies supported by stakeholders will be used in WP5, so stakeholders are involved from the conception of the experimental design to really address their challenges and needs (responsible research).

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Lead Beneficiary	Deliverable Author(s)
UPCT	Raúl Zornoza [UPTC] David Fernández-Calviño [UVIGO] Lieven Waeyenberge [EV-ILVO] Stefan Schrader [TI] Krista Peltoniemi [LUKE] Merrit Shanskiy [EULS]
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1 Introduction

The main agronomic problems faced within various European cropping systems and related end-users' needs in the different pedoclimatic regions across the EU were identified in Task 2.1 by performance of surveys and the creation of discussion groups with relevant stakeholders (researchers, farmers, agronomic technicians in companies, agribusiness, manufacturers, NGOs, public administration, suppliers, logistics, retailers, consumers associations) in each of the six pedoclimatic regions involved in SoildiverAgro. Farmer associations and companies were contacted to involve in this process as many types of stakeholders as possible. These discussion groups, in fact, were the input for the creation of the SoildiverAgro Community (Task 8.3) as part of the multi-actor approach and for ensuring the further sustainability of project results.

Task 2.2 was designed as a complement of the information extracted from Task 2.1, providing key information for proposing alternative management practices to be assessed in WP5 and WP6. An exhaustive process of data mining, literature review and meta-analysis has been performed to identify the main soil biodiversity related challenges in European cropping systems as well as possible management practices and cropping systems to overcome them. Knowledge gaps were identified, in particular in the field of agricultural soil biodiversity in relation with management practices and provision of ecosystems services, with publication of an E-book and a scientific manuscript with the meta-analysis outcomes.

Thus, to close the loop with stateholders engagement, multi-actor approach and decision-making within WP2, task 2.3 has been conceived to present the outcomes from Tasks 2.1 and 2.2 (literature review, meta-analysis, surveys, discussion groups) to stakeholders in each case pedoclimatic region, by organization of participatory regional workshops to engage them in an open plenary discussion about possible management practices cropping systems to be tested in the field. These workshops were organized and chaired by the six Regional Coordinators. The aim of these regional workshops was to identify potential cropping systems, agricultural practices and strategies to be used in synergistic combination for soil biodiversity enhancement, acknowledging the fact that the adoption of a single systems/practice/strategy would not be enough to face all the identified agronomic, socioeconomic and environmental problems while overcoming technical constraints, economic costs and social acceptance. In fact, the final list of proposed management practices for each pedoclimatic region to be implemented in WP5 was the outcomes of these workshops. The selection of the final cropping system with related management practices to be tested in WP5 was discussed in each workshop with the stakeholders. This procedure involves that only those strategies supported by stakeholders will be used in WP5, so stakeholders are involved from the conception of the experimental design to really address their challenges and needs (responsible research).

This deliverables gathers the minutes of the six different Regional Workshops organized by the Regional Coordinatos in each pedoclimatic region, showing the procedure, the topcis discussed and the agreements reached.

2 REGIONAL WORKSHOP: MEDITERRANEAN SOUTH

2.1. Objectives of the regional workshop

The workshop, conceived as an informative and discussion session was held by SoildiverAgro partners UPCT and ASAJA, addressed to all stakeholders and people interested on soil biodiversity and sustainable agriculture. This interaction with local stakeholders forms part of a multi-actor approach set up from the beginning of the project, that involves and looks for the interaction of key stakeholders during all project lifetime. Hence, the main goals of the workshop were to:

- ✓ show all results achieved during the first year of the project in WP2, showing the outcomes of a general literature research, data-mining, meta-analysis, surveys and discussions groups, and
- ✓ present the experimental design of the two case studies implemented in the Region of Murcia (CS1 and CS2) for WP5 and WP6, based on the participative process with stakeholders, so that we provide solutions to the cultivation of wheat and vegetables by the management of soil biodiversity, in search of finding the relationship between soil biological groups and crop production and quality.

2.2. Agenda of the event

Date: 29/09/2020

Time: 18:00 to 19:30

Venue: online platform Microsoft Teams

18:00. Presentation of SoildiverAgro project and the objective of the meeting

18:10. eBook "Interactions between agricultural management and soil biodiversity: an overview of current knowledge"

18:15. Relationship between microbial abundance and sustainable management practices: state of the art through a global meta-analysis

18:25. Outcomes of the surveys and discussion groups about the problems and solutions for the cultivation of wheat and potato in the Mediterranean region.

18:40. Experimental design in CS1 and CS2

2.3. Description of the event

The meeting was followed by 12 people beside presenters (19 people in total). Attendees were mostly agricultural technicians and farmers, followed by researchers.

Raul Zornoza, the Mediterranean Regional Coordinator started the meeting introducing the overall concept of the project, the general objective, and the aim of this event. After this, Eva Lloret explained how a literature review has been performed globally to assess the effects of agricultural management and soil biodiversity, with the aim of publishing the eBook "Interactions between agricultural management and soil biodiversity: an overview of current knowledge", addressed to agricultural technicians and

consultants, easy to understand. We informed that the eBook will be launched first in English, and translated afterwards into Spanish for Spanish speakers. All updates will be available on the project website and social networks. We encouraged the attendees to follow us actively. After this intervention, Alicia Morugán-Coronado showed the main results of a data-mining and global meta-analysis performed with scientific articles to assess the relationship between microbial abundance and sustainable management practices, showing that rotations, organic fertilization and minimum tillage were the practices with highest positive effects on total microbial biomass and fungal and bacterial abundance in soils.

The workshop continued with the presentation of the results of the surveys and discussion groups about the problems and solutions for the cultivation of wheat and potato in the Mediterranean region. Javier Calatrava indicated that the survey to stakeholders has helped to identify the most relevant agri-environmental problems and related end-users' needs in each of the two case studies of SoildiverAgro in the Region of Murcia and to assess the practical potential for the integration of farming practices that enhance soil biodiversity in the different cropping systems. The agri-environmental problems and objectives for actions identified are consistent with the specific nature of the agricultural system analysed in each case study. Most relevant priorities for action identified by stakeholders are concerned with the improvement of soil conditions, mostly organic matter content, structure and fertility, but also with the control of pest, diseases and weeds. The preferred soil conservation practices seem to be, in general, more oriented towards improving soil conditions than to avoiding soil loss. More precisely, crop diversification and the addition of solid organic matter are perceived as the most effective alternatives. Javier Calatrava also indicated that the results in this survey were presented to a wider audience of stakeholders in two participatory discussion groups, one for potato and the other for wheat, where they engaged into a plenary discussion that confirmed the suitability of the preferred farming practices to cope with the major agro-environmental problems in each cropping system.

Irene Ollio showed to the audience the experimental design established in CS1 (vegetables) and CS2 (wheat) for WP5 according to project objectives and outcomes from the stakeholders participation through surveys and discussion groups. The experimental designs are based on the addition to the soil of organic matter and plant growth promoting bacteria and free fungi, associated to reduced external fertilization with the aim of enhance beneficiary soil microbial groups and decrease the dependence on external inputs. Crop rotations will be applied in both case studies as a sustainable strategy to enhance soil biodiversity, increase soil quality and fertility and reduce the incidence of diseases and pests.

After all presentations, there was a 30 min discussion among participants, discussing the efficiency of the measures and practices adopted in CS1 and CS2, identifying strengths and limitations. We discussed about how soil should be sampled, how pesticides should be used, how machinery can affect crop development and the success of the project, in what way organic matter should be applied to the soil

2.4. Main outcomes of the Regional Workshop

This Workshop was established to approve the experimental design of the two case studies of the Mediterranean Region (CS1 and CS2), which will be gathered in Deliverable 2.4. Experimental Design of the Cropping Systems and Management Practices to be Tested. After the presentation and discussion, it was agreed that the experimental design will be as followed:

- CS1: With the objective to increase soil nutrient availability and soil water retention capacity and reduce soil-borne diseases/pests incidence in potato production, there will be a rotation of potato, broccoli, melon and potato during three years. In addition, there will be a reduction of 30% in external fertilization (as established in the EU Strategy from Farm to Fork) by addition of plant growth promoting bacteria and free fungi, in order to assess their efficiency in increasing soil fertility and decreasing the incidence of soil-borne diseases.
- CS1: With the objective to increase soil nutrient availability and soil water retention capacity and reduce soil-borne diseases/pests incidence in wheat production, there will be a rotation of wheat, rye and ervil during three years. In addition, there will be a reduction of 30% in external fertilization (as established in the EU Strategy from Farm to Fork) by addition of plant growth promoting bacteria and free fungi, in order to assess their efficiency in increasing soil fertility and decreasing the incidence of soil-borne diseases.

2.5. List of attendees (according to the name used when accessing the videoconference platform)

ZORNOZA BELMONTE, RAÚL
CALATRAVA LEYVA, JAVIER
MORUGÁN CORONADO, ALICIA
FERNÁNDEZ HERNÁNDEZ, JUAN ANTONIO
Pablo Sánchez
Eva Lloret
Pieter van Soest
Juan Manuel Cívico
CONTRERAS GALLEGO, JOSEFA
OLLIO, IRENE
MARTÍNEZ MARTÍNEZ, SILVIA
César Mota
Carlos Linares
Fuensanta López
ACOSTA AVILÉS, JOSÉ ALBERTO
GÓMEZ LÓPEZ, MARÍA DOLORES
M^a Pilar
Marcel Tasa
Jesús

3 REGIONAL WORKSHOP: LUSITANIAN

3.1. Objectives of the regional workshop

The Lusitanian regional workshop was held by UVIGO, with the support of INORDE, RRG and FEUGA, with the main objective of integrating stakeholders in case studies design and performance. The workshop was open to all stakeholders and people interested in agricultural development and soil biodiversity conservation. The interaction with local stakeholders forms part of a multi-actor approach concept, that involves and looks for the interaction of key stakeholders during all project lifetime. This interaction is considered a key factor for SoildiverAgro success. The specific objectives were to:

- ✓ Refresh/introduce stakeholders in SoildiverAgro project aims
- ✓ Show the works performed and results achieved during the 1.5 year of SoildiverAgro project, with special attention to WP2, showing the outcomes of a general literature research, data-mining, meta-analysis, surveys and discussions groups.
- ✓ Present the experimental design of the three case studies implemented in the Lusitanian Region (CS3, CS4, and CS5) and discuss with stakeholders the final case studies set up.

3.2. Agenda of the event

Date: 18/11/2020

Venue: online platform UVigo

16:00. Presentation of SoildiverAgro project and workshop objectives

16:15. Presentation of the current status of SoildiverAgro project and work to be performed during the next year.

17:00. Presentation of Lusitanian case studies (CS3, CS4 and CS5) and discussion.

3.3. Description of the event

The meeting was followed by 22 people including SoildiverAgro partners and stakeholders. Attendees were mostly researchers, followed by agricultural technicians.

David Fernández-Calviño, the SoildiverAgro project Coordinator started the meeting introducing the overall concept of the project, the general objective, and the aims the regional workshop. After this, the work performed during the first 1.5 years was briefly described. Special relevance was given to the literature review performed to assess the effects of agricultural management and soil biodiversity, and the resulting publication of the e-book "Interactions between agricultural management and soil biodiversity: an overview of current knowledge". We announced that the e-book will be launched first in English, but it will be translated to Spanish soon and placed in project website. When available, the e-book will be announced in the website and social networks.

David Fernández-Calviño also showed to the audience the experimental design established for CS3 (crop diversification), CS4 (use of mycorrhiza) and CS5 (pest alert system) according to project objectives and outcomes from the stakeholders' participation through surveys and discussion groups.

CS3 experimental design is based on the use of crop diversification and trap crops in potato fields to reduce the incidence of cyst nematode, reduce nematicides and increase crop yield and soil biodiversity.

The current rotation in the area is a simple one: potatoes/wheat. This rotation, used as a control, will be compared with a new one including a legume (cereal/legume/potatoes) and another one including a trap crop (potatoes/trap crop/potatoes). After a constructive debate, we decided to select green peas as legume, and *Solanum sisymbriifolium* as trap crops for cyst nematode. During the debate, the attendees suggested the need for checking more types of rotations and longer periods than three crop cycles. Also, the regional administration Xunta de Galiza showed interest in trap crops, suggesting to check more types of them and extend it to more experimental plots with the participation of a high number of farmers. Also, the attendees suggested the use of two types of potatoes in the experiments, resistant and no resistant to cyst nematode. These suggestions from farmers and public administration will be an important incentive for SoildiverAgro communities of practitioners' creation.

CS4 experimental design is based on the use of mycorrhiza in potato fields to reduce the incidence of common scab, decrease the use of phosphorus fertilizers, and increase crop yields and soil biodiversity. In the study area, cultivation of potatoes must be performed in very acid conditions (pH <5.0) to avoid the common scab disease. Under these conditions, P availability is very low and despite the presence of high amounts of phosphorus in the soils, the farmers in the area use big amounts of P fertilizers annually. We will check the introduction of potatoes mycorrhiza formulations in the common rotation in the area (potatoes/wheat). After discussion, we decided to check one mycorrhiza formulation based on one strain. The mycorrhiza formulation will be checked reducing P application in 50% and 100%. Also, controls without mycorrhiza and 100% P, 50% P and 0% P will be used. During the discussion, stakeholders suggested that other mycorrhiza formulations may be also checked such as those with multiple strains.

CS5 experimental design is based on the implementation of a pest alert system to reduce the use of fungicides in potato and wheat crops. After discussion we decided to check the pest alert system in the next crop rotation: potatoes/wheat/potatoes. Two treatments will be compared: conventional periodic fungicide applications, and fungicide applications based on the pest alert system. Some stakeholders suggested the possibility of test the system with two types of potatoes: resistant and non-resistant to mildew. In addition, some partners highlighted potential problems for pest/diseases detection in little plots. Therefore, they will be higher than in other case studies. Also, some farmers showed interest in applying the pest alert system on their farms.

In general, all participants agreed on the need of more workshops showing the project design and outputs, but to engage with more stakeholders, face to face workshops are needed. Moreover, farmers showed interest in participating in the SoildiverAgro Community. Tamara Rodríguez suggested all attendees to follow the project in web and social networks, and also promote it.

3.4. Main outcomes of the Workshop

This Workshop was established to approve the experimental design of the three case studies of the Lusitanian Region (CS3, CS4 and CS5), which will be better explained in Deliverable 2.4. Experimental Design of the Cropping Systems and Management Practices to be Tested. After the presentation and discussion, it was agreed that the experimental design will be as followed:

- CS3: With the objective to reduce the incidence of cyst nematodes, decrease the nematicide inputs, increase crop yield and soil biodiversity in potato production, there will be a rotation

of potato, wheat, peas and trap crops. The peas will foster increases in soil fertility and biodiversity while trap crops will attract pests, reducing their impact on the main crop.

- CS4: Use of mycorrhiza in potato fields to reduce the incidence of common scab, decrease the use of phosphorus fertilizers, increase crop yields and soil biodiversity. For this, there will be rotations of potatoes and cereal with five treatments in the potato crop: full phosphorus fertilization, half phosphorus fertilization and inoculation with mycorrhiza, no phosphorus fertilization and inoculation with mycorrhiza, half phosphorus fertilization with no mycorrhiza and no fertilization neither mycorrhiza.
- CS5: Implementation of a pest alert system to reduce the use of fungicides in potato and wheat crops and their impact on biodiversity. For this, there will be a rotation with potatoes, wheat and potatoes during three years, with addition and no addition of the alert system to reduce the use of pesticides. The alert system will be based on a Decision Support System.

3.5. list of attendees

SoildiverAgro partners (14)

David Fernández Calviño (Uvigo)
Manuel Arias Estévez (Uvigo)
Juan Carlos Nóvoa Muñoz (Uvigo)
Flora Alonso Vega (Uvigo)
Paula Pérez Rodríguez (Uvigo)
María Jesús Iglesias Briones (Uvigo)
Francisco Javier Rodríguez Rajo (Uvigo)
Carmen Seijo Coello (Uvigo)
Paul Swagemakers (Uvigo)
María Munielo Martínez (Inorde)
Nuria Lopez Araujo (Inorde)
Servando Álvarez Pousa (Inorde)
Tamara Rodríguez Silva (FEUGA)
Rubén Rodríguez Gómez (RRG)

Stakeholders (8)

Carlos Mansanet (Xunta de Galicia; public administration)
Raquel Cascallar (Grupo SOAGA; enterprise)
Jose Angel Sotelo Castro (farmer)
Jose Ramón Gil Paz (farmer)
Julio Montero (farmer)
Jose Manuel Cabido (farmer)
Amador Diaz Penin (farmer)
Jose Manuel Nieto Rogriguez (farmer)

4 REGIONAL WORKSHOP: ATLANTIC CENTRAL

4.1. Objectives of the regional workshop

In the Atlantic Central Region, different workshops were organized, at least one per case study for WP5 (CS6, CS7, CS8 and CS9), conceived as an informative and discussion session, addressed to all stakeholders and people interested on soil biodiversity and sustainable agriculture. Three Workshop for CS6 were organized by EV-ILVO, one for CS7 by Inagro, one for CS8 by PSKW, and one for CS9 by Pomona. Another workshop is still to be organised in the beginning of March for CS9 by Pomona together with EV-ILVO (see further Case-study 9). These interactions with local stakeholders forms part of a multi-actor approach set up from the beginning of the project, that involves and looks for the interaction of key stakeholders during all project lifetime. Hence, the main goal of the workshops was to present and discuss the options for the experimental design of CS6, CS7, CS8 and CS9 for WP5 and WP6, based on the participative process with stakeholders.

4.2. Agenda of the events

Date and venue: several online and locally organised (EV-ILVO, PSKW, Inagro, Pomona separately) face-to-face contacts between colleagues and direct people involved in the set-up of the case-studies between May-October 2020.

Agenda: talking through the details (each case-study separately), especially about the location, cropping cycle (planting and sowing), treatments, maintenance, sampling schedule.

4.3. Description of the event

Case study 6

EV-ILVO presented to participants the main strategies decided to be implemented in CS6. The main strategies are:

- ✓ Mixed cover crops
- ✓ Composted manure and other organic amendments
- ✓ Reduced mechanical soil treatments

The experimental design described for discussion was:

- ✓ No comparison of cover crop mixtures
- ✓ No mixed cropping of main crops as this is already planned in a Core Organic project in which INAGRO and ILVO participate.
- ✓ No comparison of mechanical soil treatments as this has been done before in few already ended projects.

The objective of this trial design is twofold. On the one hand, the effect of whether or not to treat ruminant straw manure on carbon sequestration and nitrogen efficiency, is investigated. On the other hand, it examines how the management of an evergreen cover crop has an influence on the accumulation of carbon and nitrogen, and on the nitrogen availability for the succeeding crop. Both investigations will contribute to the main research question: what is the influence on and interaction with soil organisms.

The trial will be carried out on an ILVO biological trial plot located in Melle, East-Flanders (Region of Flanders) in Belgium; 50°59'05" N, 3°47'13". It was converted in the autumn of 2010, sowing grass clover, and subsequently exploited extensively until the summer of 2017. After the destruction of grass clover in August 2017, a cover crop mixture was sown, which was roller-crimped in June 2018. The crop rotation cycles decided have been:

- ✓ Crop Cycle 1 (20-21): Potato (var. Vitabella): *Solanum tuberosum* – Planted on 9/04/2020, harvest first week of September. Cover crop mixture (*Avena sativa* and *Vicia sativa*) until May-June.
- ✓ Crop Cycle 2 (21-22): Winter Leek: *Allium ampeloprasum* - Planting in June, harvest February/March 2022.
- ✓ Crop Cycle 3 (22-23): Still to be determined, after main crop possibly a cover crop mixture or mix of wheat and fabaceae till summer of 2023
- ✓ Crop Cycle 4 (23-24), in case the project is officially extended for 6M: Still to be determined but possibly potato again, harvest end of August.
- ✓ Crop Cycle 5 (2024), in case the project is officially extended for 1Y: Still to be determined but possibly potato again, harvest end of August. If so, than another crop will be grown in crop cycle 4.

As treatments, three types of fertilization (incl. 'zero-fertilization') and 2 different managements of cover crop mixtures will be investigated as indicated in Table 4.1.

Table 4.1. Treatments proposed and agreed in CS6

Treatment	Cover crop mixture destroyed and incorporated	Cover crop mixture removed (mowing)	Farm yard manure	FYM co-composted with brown material
1	X			
2	X		X	
3	X			X
4		X		
5		X	X	
6		X		X

The cover crop mixture is suitable for animal feed, including 2 hardy and 2 non hardy plant species. The Treatment-fertilization consists of 3 variants in terms of basic fertilization: application of treated, non-

treated straw manure of goats (co-composted with brown organic material) and no basic fertilization (zero object). Fertilization is planned at three different times: (i) after grain, before sowing the green cover mixture, (ii) before planting the potatoes and (iii) the leek. Each of the two forms of basic fertilization is always applied to the same plots. In this way the effect of repeated application on soil quality, nitrogen availability and crop performance examined. Dosage of manure versus dosage of bio-composted manure will be based on an equal input of animal manure nitrogen before storage/composting or an equal P input with this basic fertilization. Compost will be prepared for the first time in spring 2019.

Cover crop management involves 2 variants, 1 variant in which the mowed cover crop is removed from the field (AFV) and 1 variant in which the cover crop is damaged before (shallow) incorporation (business as usual: BAU).

With all these treatments discussed among participants, the following experimental design, as a split-plot design with two factors (6 combined treatments) and 4 repetitions (4 blocks) was agreed (Figure 4.1). The sampling strategy agreed is depicted in Figure 4.2.

Figure 4.1. Experimental design for CS6

Case study 7

The proposed management practises were discussed with Inagro colleagues Lieven Delanote (Researcher with more than 20 years of experience in practical research and advisory in organic farming in Flanders), Franky Coopman (Researcher and advisor in soil fertilization and health) and Joran Barbry (Research leader Organic farming) during the regional workshop. It was decided to conduct the trial on one of the testing fields of the experimental farm for organic production (12 ha of fields). This farm is unique in Flanders and a driving force behind the development of organic farming in the region. The integration of this experimental farm into the large structure of Inagro also ensures a strong exchange of techniques and knowledge between the organic and traditional cultivation method.

The trial design was therefore fitted into the fixed 6-year crop rotation from the farm. This rotation consists of vegetable as well as arable crops. A root crop is followed by a cereal. A cabbage crop is then installed, followed by potatoes. The potato crop is followed by a 1 year and a half grass clover crop as a resting crop. After a final harvest of grass-clover in the spring by mowing, leek is planted after which the cycle starts again.

Because the aim of the case study is to investigate if soil biodiversity can be improved by more diverse cover crop mixtures in function of potato, it was decided to start the trial in 2020 after the cultivation of spring wheat (Figure 4.3). In both the discussion group and the regional workshop it was suggested to opt for a short cabbage crop in 2021 in order to ensure a long growing season for the green cover in the autumn. Therefore, probably cauliflower will be chosen. In 2022, potatoes will be cultivated. After potato harvest the cover crop mixtures will be sown a last time inter alia to investigate the development of the plant species and the provision of agro-ecosystem services at late sowing.

Figure 4.3: Timeline for the three-year trial in CS7

The same cover crop mixtures will be sown in the same place during the three years of the trial. With the discussion group it was decided to compare cover crop mixtures consisting of a large number of species with cover crops mixtures consisting of much less. The participants also suggested some useful tools for choosing the species for the cover crop mixtures. Ultimately, the final types of cover crop mixtures were decided internally with the Inagro colleagues. The discussion group concluded, for example, that phacelia (*Phacelia tanacetifolia*) as Business as usual (BAU) could be a good choice, but also a two species- mix with phacelia. The regional consultation showed that mixtures of two species, including phacelia, are the most common practice. Black oat (*Avena strigosa*) is often chosen as a second species. Indeed, farmers often choose a mixture that ensures that land is recognised as an ecological focus area in order to receive a subsidy (greening measures of the European Common Agricultural Policy (CAP)).

Besides the BAU following crop mixtures were chosen:

- ✓ Phacelia+ Egyptian clover
- ✓ Five species- mixture: Phacelia+ Black oat+ Egyptian clover+ Winter vetch+ Fodder radish
- ✓ Twelve species- mixture: Phacelia+ Black oat+ Egyptian clover+ Summer vetch+ Fodder radish+ Forage radish (Tillage radish)+ Pea+ Lupin+ Serradella+ Niger+ Alsike clover+ Flax

As a diversification of the cover crop, the number of species was raised with attention to the addition of leguminous species. Leguminous species can give the cover crop mixture a greater value as a green manure due to their symbiosis with bacteria that fix N from the air. In general, almost only frost-sensitive species were chosen so that the destruction in spring is easy in function of the planting of the chosen early main crops.

Since 2016, Controlled Traffic Farming has been used on the Inagro organic farm. All the work during the growing season is done with an adjusted tractor (fig. 2) with RTK-GPS in order to preserve the 3m wide planting beds from structural damage. In addition, no more ploughing has been carried out since (Reduced tillage). This means that in spring the green cover remains will be destroyed and the soil will be prepared in this way. If, due to the mild winters as in recent years, many biomass remains of the frost sensitive green covers, they will be clapped before cutting off superficially and working in the soil with a precision cultivator (3-5 cm). In addition only subsoiling and rotary hoeing will be done before planting the main crop. After the harvest of the main crop the same tools will be used to prepare the seed bed for the cover crops.

Usually farmyard manure and/or Organic Plant Fraction (OPF, NPK: 11-0-5) is used on the farm as fertilisation. Type and dose is usually decided on the basis of a soil sample and an estimation of N-mineralisation of SOM and crop residues. The discussion group urged that the use of leguminous cover crops should certainly will have to be taken into account during the experimental years because they possibly deliver an additional supply of nitrogen which would reduce the need for fertilisation. In the regional workshop there was also a consensus to include the N-content of the cover crop biomass in the decision making of the type and dose of the fertilisation used in the years to come.

The discussion group stressed out the importance of good initial sampling of the soil biodiversity. This has been taken into account as far as possible. In the regional workshop, the timing of the other three samples was then determined. Because it is important to sample at the same time (in the same period) every year, it was decided to do this every time after the growing season of the green cover. So just after terminating the cover crop/destroying the cover crop residues in spring.

Case study 8

The different treatments (see Table 4.2) of the CS8 were largely outlined in the project proposal. In the discussion group and mostly during this regional meeting, the attendees decided about the factors of study and how they are elaborated in each treatment. The output of this resulted already in what is represented beneath in Table 4.2.

Table 4.2. Factors of study and their implementation in each treatment.

	1 – Conv intensive (= Control)	2 – Conv extensive	3 – Org intensive	4 – Org extensive
Cropping system	Conventional	Conventional	Organic	Organic
Tillage system	Inverting	Reduced	Inverting	Reduced
Fertilisation	Chemical fertilizer	Chemical fertilizer + Compost	Organic fertilizer + Slurry/manure	Organic fertilizer + Manure/compost
Use of cover crops	/	Yes	/	Yes

The trial fields are located on existing trial sites of the involved partner (PSKW). A part is chosen with no significant soil disturbance in recent past, which is cultivated uniformly and more or less representing the standard management of the region for at least the last two years. A broad crop rotation is compulsory in organic cultivation, the first year is decided to plant leek in June, which gave us the flexibility and opportunity to delay the discussion groups because of the covid-19 crisis. Second and third year celery and a cabbage crop will be installed. These three crops are major outdoor crops in this region.

The precise elaboration is decided according to the management of the trial centre in consultation with the colleagues of the trial centre. On the organic fields an animal slurry application on part of the field was already done before installation of the trial fields. To meet the regulation for organic production the second treatment necessarily needed an animal manure application. Next trial years the fertilisation strategy is adapted to the expectations of the discussion group to a more plant-based fertilisation for the extensive treatment. The feasibility of the trial implementation was discussed half June 2020 with Onno Bes, responsible at PSKW for open field mechanisation. Inter alia, the timing and use of machinery for soil tillage and the incorporation of crop covers and residues were discussed to assure a successful planting. Figure 4.4 shows the eventual implementation and timeline for the four different treatments during the course of the trial. Crop rotation, cover crops, fertilisation and soil tillage is included.

Figure 4.4. Timeline for each treatment in the three-year SoildiverAgro trial in CS8

The type of cover crops is decided in function of the timing of installation and the advice of the discussion group. In spring, a fast growing crop is needed and the N-fixation of the clover is useful for the main crop. The incorporation needs to be sufficiently early before installation of the main crop, to assure a successful planting. Main machinery for soil cultivation that will be used for this trial are a teeth cultivator, a spading machine for inverting tillage and a rotary cultivator for crop incorporation.

The organic fields where a.o. the SoildiverAgro trials are located were already visited by some interested farmers by means of a guided visit organised in August by the case study coordinator, Proefstation voor de Groenteteelt. In small groups of only three farmers at a time, wearing a mask, this visit was possible during this epidemic. Little differences can yet be seen between the different

treatments. The soil biotic and abiotic analysis in fall and the harvest afterwards will reveal if there could already be seen differences between management practices in this first year.

Image 4.1. Guided visit with small group of farmers (left) and leek plants in the trial on 1/9/2020 (right)

Case study 9

Pomona is a cooperative agroforestry company with a local network of farmers and consumers. The goal is that the farmers provide for 80% of the food supply for the customers. The farmers follow the agro-ecological principles for sustainable food production with application of green organic matter, cover crops incorporated after destruction and reduced tillage. In this respect, Pomona has decided in consultation with their partners, to investigate the use of locally produced, whether or not fermented, organic material on their fields to improve soil health, especially biodiversity, and reduce the amount of waste (circular economy).

During a discussion with most of the Pomona partners and some volunteers/customers, it was decided to organise the case-study on a field of approximately 1,2 ha located in the North of Flanders (Beveren, East-Flanders, N51°16'03.5" E4°11'03,6"). It will be divided into 3 rows of 8m upon 300m of which each row will contain 4 plots. Thus, in total there will be 12 plots (3 treatments, 4 repeats).

Image 4.2. View of the case-study 9 experimental site.

Three treatments are subject of the field trial. Two types of green manure and “zero” application (BAU) will be compared with each other to assess the impact on C-content and improvement of the soil structure and biodiversity. The sources of green manure are locally produced compost and fermented organic matter (bokashi). The organisation Pomona has strong expectations on this kind of organic matter as fermented organic waste has some additional advantages: improved microbial activity providing natural antibiotics, essential micro-nutrients and plant growth hormones.

At the moment, *Triticum spelta* is growing on the entire field trial as green manure crop and to harvest the grains in August 21 for the production of flour and finally bread. More details about the subsequent crop rotation are not available yet as a final discussion will be continued during the first weeks of March. The reason for this delay is the fact that Pomona has faced some organisation problems during 2020: Pomona lost one of the cooperating farmers some months ago. This farmer suddenly decided not to participate with Pomona anymore while it was agreed that he was going to help with the execution and maintenance of the case-study on one of his own fields. This field was suddenly not available anymore. However, Pomona also has fields of their own and they decided to set-up the case-study on one of those fields. Because Pomona is an organization run by non-farmers or agronomists, for practical matters of course they prefer an agreement with a farmer to guide and help them through the process of maintaining a field trial. Recently, they have made such an agreement with another farmer to maintain the case-study as he is interested in the goals of the SoildiverAgro project. During the first weeks of March, a final meeting at the field trial with a Pomona representative, the farmer and 2 agronomist from EV-ILVO will be held to decide upon the crop rotation and sampling schedule, and to go through the details once more.

4.4. Main outcomes of the Workshop

Several Workshops were established to approve the experimental design of all case studies of the Atlantic Region (CS6, CS7, CS8 and CS9), which will be better explained in Deliverable 2.4. Experimental Design of the Cropping Systems and Management Practices to be Tested. After the presentation and discussion, it was agreed that the experimental design will be as followed:

- CS6: Soil management strategies to improve soil quality while minimizing external input of N and P in potato crops. The rotation will consist of potato, oat/vetch, winter leek, wheat, potato. To reduce the use of external inputs, three types of fertilization and two manages of cover crops will be tested: cover crop incorporated versus cover crop removed; application of farmyard manure and farmyard manure co-composted with brown material versus 'zero' application.
- CS7. Use of cover crop mixtures to increase soil biodiversity in potato crops. For this, there will be a rotation of spring wheat, cauliflower and potato. There will be four factors of study with regard to crop mixtures: i) phacelia and black oat; ii) phacelia and Egyptian clover; iii) phacelia, black oat, Egyptian clover, vetch and radish; and iv) phacelia, black oat, Egyptian clover, vetch, radish, pea, lupin, seradella, niger, Alsike clover and flax.
- CS8. Comparison among conventional intensive, conventional extensive and organic vegetable farming to assess the system that better increases soil biodiversity. In all systems there will be a crop rotation of leek, celery and cauliflower, during three years. In the intensive conventional system there will be chemical fertilization and no cover crops, in the extensive conventional system there will be chemical fertilization and addition of compost, and in the organic system there will be addition of organic fertilizers and manure.
- CS9. Improving agro-ecological wheat production by application of different sources of green manure. The crop rotation is not yet fixed as it will depend on the final workshop with the new farmer (see before). However, it was already agreed upon to test 2 types of green manure (locally produced compost and fermented organic matter (bokashi)) with "zero" application (BAU).

4.5. List of attendees

CS6 – EV-ILVO: Lieven Waeyenberge (senior researcher, co-coordinator, soil and earthworm sampling, pest and diseases assessments), Thibault De Volder (technician, soil and earthworm sampling), Koen Willekens (senior researcher, coordinator, cropping cycle and management), Luc De Jaegher (technician, planting and sowing, soil sampling, crop yield and quality, case-study maintenance), Jolien Bracke (researcher), Hilde Wustenberghs (senior researcher, expert in agro-economic and social aspects), Jo Bijtbeier (senior researcher, expert in agro-economic and social aspects), Nancy de Sutter (senior technician, nematode and earthworm taxonomic expert, soil and earthworm sampling, pest and diseases assessments), Karoline d'Haene (researcher, research platform sustainable fertilization), Monique van Oeckel ("Vlaamse Landmaatschappij", coordinator project "optimisation of fertilization strategies in organic agriculture").

CS7 – Inagro: Jasper Vanbesien (researcher, coordinator, soil and earthworm sampling, pest and diseases assessments), Lieven Delanote (Researcher, over 20 years of experience in practical research

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and advisory in organic farming in Flanders), Franky Coopman (Researcher and advisor in soil fertilization and health), Joran Barbry (Research leader Organic farming), Tom Decuypere (company leader of the Organic Research Station, cropping cycle and management), Brecht Vandenbroucke (agricultural technician, planting and sowing, soil and earthworm sampling, case-study maintenance), Torsten Martens (agricultural technician, planting and sowing, soil and earthworm sampling, case-study maintenance), Johan Rapol (agricultural technician, planting and sowing, soil and earthworm sampling, case-study maintenance), Philippe France, (technician, earthworm sampling)

CS8 – PSKW: Sander Fleerackers (researcher, coordinator, soil and earthworm sampling, pest and diseases assessments), Onno Bes (agricultural technician, expert mechanical management, case-study management, maintenance and planning), Matthias Cooreman (agricultural technician, soil and earthworm sampling, crop assessment), Kris Vandesteene (agricultural technician, soil and earthworm sampling, crop assessment), Noémie Hisette (Researcher).

CS9 – Pomona: Lieven Bauwens (coordinator, planning and management), Marc temmermans (coordinator, planning and management), Stéphanie De Caluwé (farmer, case-study maintenance), Rudi Hennissen (farmer, case-study maintenance), Tim De Roeck (adviser, organisation), Bart Van Gasse (technical operator, volunteer) and Ann Van Hoye (administration). As mentioned before, a final workshop will be held in March to set the details about the crop rotation and sampling schedule together with EV-ILVO.

5 REGIONAL WORKSHOP: CONTINENTAL

5.1. Objectives of the regional workshop

The workshop, conceived as an informative and discussion session was held by SoildiverAgro partners Johann Heinrich von Thünen-Institut in cooperation with FAR, addressed to all stakeholders and people interested on soil biodiversity and sustainable agriculture. Hence, the main goals of the workshop were to show and discuss the results during the discussion discussions groups, and present and agree the experimental design of the two case studies implemented in the region (CS10 and CS11) for WP5 and WP6, based on the participative process with stakeholders.

5.2. Agenda of the event

Date: 03/11/2020

Time: 13:15 to 14:30

Venue: online

5.3. Description of the event

The meeting was chaired by Stefan Schrader (TI), who is the Continental Regional Coordinator. He showed the results from Task 2.1 and Task 2.2, highlighting the experimental designed proposed for CS10 and CS11, with the different treatments, approaches and replications. The experimental design for both CSs was confirmed and agreed (see Deliverable D2.4). For CS10, the management measures in the different treatments are still under discussion with a focus on different undersown crops. Details will be clarified with participating farmers during the next months before the starting on Spring 2021. For CS11, there was a consent on management measures in the different treatments. In addition to the planned measurements, data on mycotoxins (here: deoxynivalenol) in grains will be considered.

5.4. Main outcomes of the Workshop

This Workshop was established to approve the experimental design of the two case studies of the Continental Region (CS10 and CS11), which will be better explained in Deliverable 2.4. Experimental Design of the Cropping Systems and Management Practices to be Tested. After the presentation and discussion, it was agreed that the experimental design will be as followed:

- CS10: Biocontrol of soil-borne phytopathogenic fungi by fungivorous soil fauna communities in potato cropping systems to evaluate whether reduced external inputs and changes in management strengthen soil self-regulation processes and contribute to fungal plant pest control. For this there will be crop rotations among potato, winter wheat, rapeseed and winter wheat. We will compare two cropping systems (conventional vs organic), two rates of pesticides and two rates of fertilization.
- CS11. Potential of plant diversity to promote intrinsic soil self-regulation processes and to enhance fungivorous soil fauna communities in wheat cropping systems. For this purpose, there will be a rotation of winter wheat, winter barley, maize and winter wheat. There will be a conventional farming with seeding rate and pesticide application according to local farming practices, an extensive farming with seeding rate reduced with no pesticide addition

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and a diversified extensive farming with seeding rate reduced, no pesticide application and clover species mix a cover crops.

5.5. List of attendees

Research center: Johann Heinrich von Thünen-Institut (TI): Stefan Schrader (regional coordinator), Christine van Capelle

Enterprise: Flächenagentur Rheinland GmbH: Birte Tschentke, David-Alexander Bind

6 REGIONAL WORKSHOP: NEMORAL

6.1. Objectives of the regional workshop

The workshop, conceived as an informative and discussion session was held by the Regional Coordinator, EESTI, addressed to all stakeholders and people interested on soil biodiversity and sustainable agriculture. Hence, the main goals of the workshop were to show and discuss the results during the discussion discussions groups, and present and agree the experimental design of the case study implemented in the region (CS12) for WP5 and WP6, based on the participative process with stakeholders.

6.2. Agenda of the event

Date: 30/10/2020

Time: 10:00 to 12:00

Venue: online through platform BigBlueButton

10:00 – 10:15 Introduction to SoildiverAgro and aim of the regional meeting (Merrit Shanskiy)

10:15 – 11:00 Introduction of survey results and discussion with stakeholders on main soil management problems and practices to address those (Anne Pöder)

11:00 – 11:20 Overview on case study 12.1: pesticides accumulation (Merrit Shanskiy)

11:20 – 11:40 Overview on case study 12.2: control of phytopathogenic fungi (Kaire Loit)

11:40 – 11:45 Closing remarks (Merrit Shanskiy)

11:40- – 12:00 Free discussion with farmers and other participants, who had specific issues or questions to researchers related to soil management, scientific research, cooperation etc. and wanted to discuss those in a small group.

6.3. Description of the event

The meeting was followed by 26 participants. The meeting started with presentation of Estonian coordinator Merrit Shanskiy on the overall aims of the SoildiverAgro project, agenda of the day, the project activities carried out so far, the data collected and how the data will be used, the planned future activities and research agenda.

The second section was discussion of agronomic and soil management challenges, incl. effective tillage, fertilization, soil conservation, disease and pest control practices. The discussion combined presentation of surveys results by Anne Pöder followed by round table discussion after each topic in which participants were asked if those results are applicable for them, what is their experience, what kind of question and information was missing and what topics should be added to the research agenda of the project.

General agreement on in the discussion of agronomic problems was that the problems pointed out by potato survey apply to cereal farmers as well, but as explained by two farmers detailing their practices, the issue is that the soil conditions even within the same farm differ greatly, thus the farmer has to adjust its practices depending on the plot and this also makes difficult to give answers to the questionnaire that does not specify this issue. Two farmers raised the issue that not the scarcity of rainfall, but the erratic weather patterns are the biggest challenge. Thus water drainage solutions should receive more attention. For an organic producer, the fungal disease was problematic. Another farmer discussed the challenge of

finding optimal use of fertilization and nutrients in practice and question on how to easily observe soil fertility. Additional feedback was that project should address the topics of leaching and soil acidity and liming in Estonia and practical measurement of soil biodiversity.

Feedback on the prioritization of goals to address the agronomic problems showed that the farmers found relevant to adjust the practice according to specific issue and this complicated the assessments in the questionnaire. The consensus was that there is a need to have a holistic approach to soil management as the topics surveyed with questionnaire – increase of organic matter content, water infiltration, soil fertility, load carrying capacity and soil biota – are interconnected issues as with suitable management practices improving one will improve another. Additionally, the importance of topics of Ca content in soil and plant diseases, effect of soil pH on nutrient assimilation and soil biota were indicated in the feedback.

Discussion of question of effective tillage and fertilization practices included sharing of farmers' experience with no till and minimum tillage, researchers' results on testing pesticides in different tillage. The need for holistic approach was demonstrated by a farmer sharing experience on pesticide use and disease control by explaining how they are making effort in combing crop diversification, disease resistant varieties, optimal pesticide use to improve soil management. It was pointed out the crop diversification is a long term strategy, while pesticide use and disease control tend to be more urgent and short term solutions. There was agreement that conventional farming in the region needs pesticides, but how to achieve the optimal usage requires attention. Crop diversification was seen as most effective for soil conservation; but the addition of organic matter depends also on such factors as its availability. The feedback also emphasized that the more attention should be paid to organic matter content in soil and not removing straw/plant residues from the fields. Participants mentioned the utilization of catchcrops as input to organic matter that is the source of nutrients and moisture regulation in soil and right crops that help to sustain soil fertility and health, demonstrated by the comment from a farmer "The healthier the soil, the healthier the plant". The importance of addressing the topic of liming in the project was again brought up in discussion of two farmers and a scientist.

The discussion was continued in the overview of the Case study 12 in nemoral region. The first case study was presented by Merrit Shanskiy and focuses on pesticides accumulation rate in the litter layer of no-till cereal fields and on management impact to soil biodiversity with the goal to improve pesticide application and soil biodiversity. Farmers were interested in where the field trials are conducted, the time frame and how it is related to their challenges and pesticide use. Scientists from other institutions wanted to discuss the technical implementation of the tests incl. taking of soil samples, while producers' questions were on pesticide use.

Second case study focuses on the control of phytopathogenic fungi and was presented by Kaire Loit, who started with technical overview on the use of spore sampler to study the spread of spores by air in order to improve the pest monitor and control. Producers in particular had additional question on how often the collected spore samples are analyzed and how this can affect the practical use of the data by farmers.

In the closing remarks, the further plans, incl. that need to collect data on socioeconomic factors, and input for other WPs was explained.

Organizers gave those, who were interested in discussing different concerns related to the topic or their research opportunity to do that in a small session following the closing remarks.

6.4. Main outcomes of the Workshop

This Workshop was established to approve the experimental design of the case study of the Nemoral Region (CS12), which will be better explained in Deliverable 2.4. Experimental Design of the Cropping Systems and Management Practices to be Tested. After the presentation and discussion, it was agreed that the experimental design will be as followed:

- CS12a: Effect of pesticide rate application on soil biodiversity. For this, there will be a rotation among winter wheat, oilseed rape and fava bean, with different pesticide rates and tillage systems (no-till, reduced till and conventional ploughing).
- CS12b: Control of phytopathogenic fungi by direct identification of air-borne inoculum to reduce the use of fungicides. For this, there will be a rotation between potato and wheat, and there will be spore traps above the crop canopy to detect fungi and only apply fungicides when needed

6.5. List of attendees

Name	Position	Organization/farm
Ain Ahlberg	farmer	Tohvri Farm
Alar Astover	scientist	Estonian University of Life Sciences
Anne Põder	scientist	Estonian University of Life Sciences
Avo Toomsoo	scientist	Estonian University of Life Sciences
Enn Leedu	scientist	Estonian University of Life Sciences
Evelin Pihlap	scientist	Agricultural Research Center
Henn Raave	scientist	Estonian University of Life Sciences
Jaan Ahlberg	farmer	Avanduse Agro Ltd.
Jüri Patune	farmer	Sukahärma Märdi Farm
Kadri Allik	scientist	Agricultural Research Center
Kaire Loit	scientist	Estonian University of Life Sciences
Kaire Rannik	scientist	Estonian University of Life Sciences
Karin Kauer	scientist	Estonian University of Life Sciences
Karli Sepp	scientist	Estonian Crop Research Institute
Liina Talgre	scientist	Estonian University of Life Sciences
Maire Nurmet	farmer	Sole proprietor
Mari Ivask	scientist	Estonian University of Life Sciences
Merit Sutri	scientist	Estonian University of Life Sciences
Merrit Shanskiy	scientist	Estonian University of Life Sciences
Olav Kreen	farmer	Rabaveere Farm Ltd.
Priit Penu	scientist	Agricultural Research Center
Raimo Kölli	scientist	Estonian University of Life Sciences
Roosi Soosaar	farmer & NGO	Smart Agri Ltd. & MTÜ Põllukultuuride Klaster
Sandra Pärnpuu	farmer	Vetissilla Ltd.
Taavi Tobreluts	farmer	Pirmastu Ltd.

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Tõnis Ajaots	farmer	Rannu Seeme Ltd.
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7 REGIONAL WORKSHOP: BOREAL

7.1. Objectives of the regional workshop

The workshop, conceived as an informative and discussion session was held by the Regional Coordinator, Luke, addressed to all stakeholders and people interested on soil biodiversity and sustainable agriculture. Hence, the main goals of the workshop were to show and discuss the results during the discussion discussions groups, and present and agree the experimental design of the case studies implemented in the Boreal region (CS13, CS14 and CS15) for WP5 and WP6, based on the participative process with stakeholders.

7.2. Agenda of the event

Date: 20/03/2020

Time: 09:00 to 12:00

Venue: online

09:00 – 09:15 Welcome and current stage of the SoildiverAgro project

09:15 – 10:00 Results of the questionnaires and summary about the discussion groups in WP2

10:00 – 10:30 Final plans an set up for the case studies in WP5

10:30 – 11:15 About the sampling and analyses in WP5

11:15 – 12:00 General Discussion

7.3. Description of the event

Regional coordinator Krista Peltoniemi (KP) from Luke welcomed altogether 17 project members from Luke, Kilpiä and Tyynelä farms and Petla to join the regional meeting. Meeting was held as online via skype connection because of the corona virus thread and official instruction to work at home. She explained briefly the ongoing tasks and next steps of the current work packages in the project. Main focus of the meeting was to finalize the plans for the boreal case studies conducted in WP5. KP informed project members that because virus threat all-over the Europe other partners in Europe may not be able to conduct all the current tasks this year (discussion groups, regional workshop, establishment of the case studies) our project coordinator David Fernández has asked from commission permission to prolong the project for one year. She will inform Finnish project partners, when she gets further information about the enquiry from DF. Many tasks of the project however most likely will be postponed further in the future as well as the general assembly planned in Tartu in Estonia in July. KP told about the news story about the SoildiverAgro project which is now published in the front page in public website of Luke (www.luke.fi available also in English). She also told that most WP2 related tasks are quite nicely finished or at least in the final process for boreal region. The E-book is under a final process, results from the questionnaires from Finnish respondents are ready, and that discussion groups for stakeholders dealing with the results and problem concerning the case studies were successfully organized in good-spirit by multiactor-approach on March Thu the 5th at hotel Krapi in Tuusula. Discussion groups contained 22 participants including the project members. A brief report about the Finnish discussion groups have been sent to Javier. Everybody was a bit worried how to be able to conduct all the field work this summer if the corona threat goes worse. Farmer partners reminded that cropping cycle would be perfect this year to start monitoring and sampling case study fields, thus everybody agreed that we try to begin and conduct the

field studies as planned already this year. But of course we have to change plans and follow the instruction given by authorities if the virus threat situation goes worse. KP told that plastic chambers will be put in the case study field plots in the beginning of studies and gas samples taken through the growing period from May to October. Organizers gave those, who were interested in discussing different concerns related to the topic or their research opportunity to do that in a small session following the closing remarks.

Eija Pouta (EP), a leader of WP6 from Luke, introduced and summarized briefly the main result as graphs obtained from the stakeholders from the boreal region. EP verified that answers quite nicely showed that our case study plans and ideas are among the real problems indicated in boreal region. Sari Autio and Sari Iivonen presented everyone the general outputs from the discussion groups. General opinion among the project members about the discussion groups event was that it was successful and participants active and their conversations lively and useful. They also confirmed that there had been a few very good suggestions to improve the case studies which will be taken into account. Sari A described how the used ex ante questionnaire form was a bit too complicated to fill for many stakeholders. EP has sent the results about the form and critics raised by the form to person responsible Hilde Wustenberghs in Belgium to deal with it.

First, Anna Sipilä (AS) from Petla introduced everyone the plans for the case study 13 and 14 for the early potato. She told that both case studies will be conducted in early potato fields of the same farm located in Laitila, southwestern Finland. For case study 13 "Increase of soil biodiversity through amendment of forest based organic material in potato crops" two different types of organic amendment products obtained by Soilfood company are introduced in the early potato field after the harvest in the first year and then plots are monitored for the next three years. In the case study 15 "Use of catch crop in farmed early potatoes fields" mix of rye and westerwold ryegrass and honeyflower as other catch crop are sown in the early potato field after the potato harvest over the winter. Control plots do not receive any catch crops. Then Tuomas Mattila (TM) from Kilpiä farm partner and Juuso Joona (JJ) from Tyynelä farm partner introduced their field set ups for the case study 14 "Contrasting continuous plant cover with inversion tillage in wheat fields". TM explained that randomized block design will be used for Kilpiä field with four replicate plots with minimum tillage as control and conventional mouldboard ploughing as treatment. Kilpiä case study field site has been under the organic farming since 2005 and in the first and third sampling year there will spring wheat as the cropping cycle plant. TM also told that he will be using TOMST soil sensors to monitor temperature and moisture condition in the plot. Same or similar sensors will be used in other case study fields. JJ explained that he cannot apply block design in his Tyynelä farm field site because of the heterogeneity of the site, thus we will have to build sample plots in another way to these fields where minimum tilled field site with direct drilling is next to the conventional mouldboard ploughed field site. JJ told that sites represent same soil type and are comparable with each other. JJ sees that these kinds of experiment with randomized blocks having scientific point of view cannot be always conducted in the farm scale, thus compromises have to be made. There was quite a much discussion about Tyynelä field how to sample it properly without the blocks and we decided to ask one of the Luke's experts for help who has experience on various field KP reminded that partners responsible for the case study set up should use power point template for the final set up plan with all the details, which eventually should be sent to the coordinator

KP briefly went through the soil sampling plan and gas sample procedure for the case studies. She told others about the procedure that samples from the case study 14 field will be collected at the flag leaf stage of the wheat and for potato case studies the more suitable sampling time will be in the autumn. Earthworm sampling will be collected in the autumn when the weather conditions are suitable (not too dry). KP reminded that sampling procedure follow the one conducted for WP3 last autumn with a few exceptions, e.g., soil volumetric sample will be collected only from one depth between the soil sampling horizon 0-20 cm.

Participants did not have any special on their mind and look forward to start the field fork for the case studies as planned if the corona threat situation does not prevent it. KP promised to inform the project members about the changes in the project if there will be any. KP closed the meeting at 12:00.

7.4. Main outcomes of the Workshop

This Workshop was established to approve the experimental design of the three case studies of the Bireak Region (CS13, CS14 and CS15), which will be better explained in Deliverable 2.4. Experimental Design of the Cropping Systems and Management Practices to be Tested. After the presentation and discussion, it was agreed that the experimental design will be as followed:

- CS13: Increase of soil biodiversity through amendment of forest based organic material in potato crops. For this, there will be a control with conventional fertilization, addition of wood fiber sludge and addition of composted pulp of mill sludge.
- CS14: Contrasting continuous plant cover with inversion tillage in wheat fields in organic farming to increase soil biodiversity. For this there will be a rotation of spring wheat, cover crop, spring wheat and cover with comparison of conventional tillage and no tillage.
- CS15: Use of catch crop in farmed potatoes fields to avoid the leakage of nutrients and so to decrease the use of external fertilizers, with estimated positive effects on soil biodiversity. For this there will be a potato crop, a potato crop with rye and ryegrass and catch crop and a potato crop with phacelia as catch crop.

7.5. List of attendees

Krista Peltoniemi (Luke)
Eija Pouta (Luke)
Tuomas Mattila (Kilpiä farm)
Juuso Joonas (Tyynelä farm)
Marjo Serenius (Petla)
Anna Sipilä (Petla)
Sari Iivonen (Luke)
Sari Autio (Luke)
Visa Nuutinen (Luke)
Marleena Hagner (Luke)
Hannu Känkänen (Luke)
Hannu Fritze (Luke)
Taina Pennanen (Luke)
Sannakajsa Velmala (Luke)

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